

Synthesis of Dimethyldialkoxysilanes

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The reaction of dimethyldichlorosilane on ethanol does not proceed to completion and is accompanied with side reactions, forming ethyl chloride and polymerised silicon derivatives¹. Successful preparation of dimethyldialkoxysilanes have been described by employing proton acceptors, e.g., pyridine², diethylaniline³, trimethylamine³.

Ammonia has been used in the synthesis of alkoxy derivatives of titanium and zirconium by the corresponding reactions of the tetrachlorides with alcohols⁴. Ammonia as a proton-acceptor has decided advantages both in view of the experimental convenience with which a reaction mixture can be saturated with anhydrous ammonia as well as in the ease with which excess ammonia can be volatilised after the reaction has been completed. The precipitate of ammonium chloride is crystalline and easy to filter. In view of the above, the preparation of a number of dimethyldialkoxysilanes has been carried out according to the following reaction:

Heat is evolved as soon as ammonia is passed in the reaction mixture of alcohol and chlorosilane and the completeness of the reaction is conveniently shown when the reaction mixture begins to cool down. It has further been found that in presence of benzene, the precipitate of ammonium chloride more readily separates as its solubility is reduced in alcohol by benzene. In view of the closeness of the boiling point of benzene with dimethyldimethoxysilane, toluene was employed successfully in the preparation of this compound.

All-glass apparatus with standard ground glass joints was used throughout the work. The alcohols were dried over metallic sodium and distilled. Benzene (B. D. H.) was first stored over sodium metal and then dried by azeotropic distillation with ethanol. Toluene (B. D. H.) was also dried over metallic sodium and then distilled. Dimethyldichlorosilane (B. D. H.) was distilled just before use. Ammonia gas (commercial) was dehydrated by bubbling it through a battery of bottles containing benzene solution of aluminium isopropoxide followed by towers packed with freshly ignited quick lime and aluminium isopropoxide.

1. Krieble and Burkhard, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2889.

2. Saur, *ibid.*, 1944, **66**, 1707.

3. Smith, Doctoral thesis 1951, Chalmers Technical High School, Gothenberg.

4. Bradley and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 290.

Analytical Method.—In view of the volatile nature of the compound and the comparatively stable nature of carbon-silicon bond, direct ignition of the compound after digestion with concentrated sulphuric acid in a platinum crucible gave low and erroneous results.

So, for the estimation of silicon, 0.1-0.3 g. of the compound was added to $A.R. H_2SO_4$ (conc., 30 ml) in a 250 ml conical flask. The flask was cooled; 5 g. each of solid ammonium sulphate (AnalaR) and ammonium nitrate (AnalaR) was added and the mixture was kept overnight. It was then heated slowly at first over a sand bath for about an hour and finally digested for 4 hours. The solution was then cooled and allowed to stand for 2 hours after being added to 300 ml of distilled water. The precipitate was filtered through a Whatman 42 filter paper, washed with water, dried, and ignited to silica.

General Method of Synthesis.—Dimethyldichlorosilane was added dropwise to an excess of alcohol with vigorous shaking. A slight warming of the reaction mixture occurred. Dry benzene was then added in sufficient amount, followed by passing of ammonia gas when the reaction took place with evolution of heat and precipitation of ammonium chloride. The bubbling of ammonia was continued till the reaction mixture cooled down. Precipitated ammonium chloride was filtered, washed with dry benzene, and the filtrate was refluxed to expel excess of ammonia gas. Excess of benzene and alcohol were then removed by distillation. Finally the compound was obtained by distillation or fractionation (as in the case of dimethyldimethoxysilane).

TABLE I

Properties of the compounds synthesised.

Silane.	Yield.	B.P.	% Silicon.	
			Found.	Reqd.
1. Dimethyldimethoxy-	59	85°	23.04	23.30
2. Dimethyldipropoxy ⁿ .	48	148-50°	15.76	15.90
3. Dimethyldipropoxy ⁱ .	50	130-35°	15.58	15.90
4. Dimethyldibutoxy ⁿ .	76	160-83°	13.71	13.73
5. Dimethyldibutoxy ^{sec} .	76	169-73°	13.76	13.73
6. Dimethyldiamyloxy ⁿ .	67	91-94°/2.5-3 mm	11.89	12.07

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